

Industry Practices in Tourism Education Institution: A Leverage and Challenge

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 25, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: December 26, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Teaching Factory, Project-Based Learning, Link And Match, Experiential Learning</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7482352</p>	<p><i>Nowadays, graduate employability has gotten more stringent because each industry has its own standards that must be met. It has an impact on educational institutions generally and specifically on vocational institutions. One of Indonesia's vocational schools, Politeknik Negeri Bali, is working to integrate industry best practices with educational practices through the Food and Beverage Teaching Factory (TeFa), which demonstrates the students' aptitude for developing food production and managing a food and beverage outlet's small business. The investigation of the TeFa's operation is the main subject of this study, which employs a qualitative methodology to determine the leverage and challenges the institution faces. The findings demonstrate that, despite the difficulties encountered in setting up the Tefa's day-to-day operations and integrating its management into the institution's overall establishment, the potential benefits gained are significant in providing students with experiences in operating and managing a small business. The TeFa is a case study object that can be examined from all angles and is easily accessible.</i></p>

Introduction

The caliber of the human resources working in the tourism sector has a significant impact on the performance of service providers. Since tourism is a worldwide industry that spans nations, international standards for product quality are anticipated. This emphasizes how crucial it is for the sector to have qualified human resources. Even while formal education is a lifelong endeavor and professional development happens while a person is employed, it is still crucial for developing competent human resources and laying the groundwork for the labor force. Nowadays, graduates' involvement in industrial activities as either entrepreneurs or hired by enterprises serves as a direct indicator of the educational institution's success. Graduates who are qualified should be swiftly assimilated and satisfy industrial needs. The product of a quality educational institution is the outcome of an effective teaching and learning process. Education institutions must develop a variety of teaching and learning techniques to maximize students' learning to achieve this objective. The results will be greatly influenced by the innovation and commitment of the lecturers as well as the support of the institution, either locally or nationally.

Vocational high schools and tertiary institutions in Indonesia offer vocational education, producing graduates with diplomas from institutions like the Polytechnic. Vocational education aims to prepare students for the workforce by providing them with the necessary knowledge, abilities, attitudes, skills, and work ethics (Sofyawati et al., 2022). Programs that boost students with the competencies, experience, insights, and networks needed to prepare them for the industry placements supporting their career development goals should be applied and supplied by the schools (Hiniker and Putnam, 2009). In order to tune in students and alumnae with work place, vocational institutions put efforts in creating a sustainability ecosystem through link and match between industry and educational institutions.

Additionally, this endeavor is made at the Bali State Polytechnic in line with the implementation of the new policy announced by the Ministry of Education and Culture, Research and Technology in Indonesia 'Merdeka belajar kampus merdeka - MBKM' (free to learn and independent campus). The relationship between educational institutions and business entities is strengthened and intensified in order to develop professional human resources that are prepared to begin working soon after graduation. Among those activities devised include: industry practitioners are invited to share their experience with students, and lecturers are encouraged to find out the most recent information about industry current practices. Aside from the traditional approach of teaching through lecturing, there are other ways to ensure that students are mastering the competencies at the cognitive, emotional, and psychometric levels throughout study time based on Bloom's taxonomy (Achmad and Prastowo, 2022). Students are encouraged to practice not just in a virtual environment but also in real-world settings. As a result, campuses are encouraged to start businesses that would benefit students' learning and campuses as the Badan Layanan Umum- BLU (Public Service Institution). This study is now being conducted

with the intention of evaluating the commercial enterprise started and run at Bali's Politeknik Negeri Tourism Department in Indonesia.

Link and Match Education Institution and Industry

Starting with the fundamental rules for structuring vocational education by Charles Prosser in 1925 (in Ali, et al., 2019), he stated that there are 16 core aspects in implementing vocational education as work education. It is assumed to be applicable when meeting the criteria as follows: (1) learning environments are created to be as similar to the workplace as feasible; (2) the process of teaching and training is carried out in the same way as operations in terms of tools or machines used; (3) preparing the students to think and work as is required in real job; (4) encouraging students to take an increased interest in learning, and everyone who needs, desires, and can profit from learning; (5) establishing mental and behavioral patterns consistently in line with job requirements; (6) having experienced lecturers and/or instructors who are competent; (7) students with a minimal level of productivity; (8) observing the needs of the labor market; (9) fostering work habits and character of students; (10) giving students a trustworthy source from the knowledge of the industry professionals; (11) providing a particular body of information in accordance with the requirements on the job market; (12) addressing the unique requirements of any group as they arise; (13) focusing on how teaching methods relate to students who fit into a given group and have certain qualities; (14) adaptable administration and management; and, (15) the availability of adequate financial assistance.

Student training during study period is an important phase as Grollmann and Rauner (2007) agree that vocational training serves as a link between the working world and the educational system. The participation of students in the outside world - the workplace, and industry to be integrated within the educational program is then one of the crucial factors to be taken into consideration (Ali et al., 2019). The Government of Indonesia strives to improve the quality of vocational graduates through the Directorate General of Vocational Higher Education by launching six vocational programs, namely: (1) developing a work culture, (2) merit and special scholarships, (3) entrepreneurship, (4) innovative learning works, (5) competency certification, and (6) development of BLUD Vocational Schools (Kemendikbud, 2020). Link-and-match is one of the policies launched by the Ministry of Education and Culture, Research and Technology of the Republic of Indonesia that has been existed and developed to increase the relevance of educational institutions as a whole to the needs of the world of work, business and industry in particular with the assistance of the new educational paradigm launched, called MBKM - Merdeka Belajar, Kampus Merdeka (free to learn and independent campus). This policy is implemented and integrated in a curriculum representing the process in which students either obtaining job experience in the industry or upgrading and/or strengthening the existing talent by learning at other universities or faculties; the study results are not only measured by grades and numerical scores. This theory is stated to be optimal if there is a reciprocal link between the user or the workplace industries and the power supply, in this case the vocational institutions (Santoso et al., 2021).

The link-and-match program is seen as a job at the skills required by the labor market of the future, which is anticipated to be a paradigm of educational orientation that is more demand-minded and centered on market needs rather than supply-minded. The link-and-match policy has two goals: one is for high school students, and the other is for college students. Particularly at the college level, it is anticipated that the industry will play a part in developing specialized training and even working with institutions to form them in accordance with the type of industry established. This approach is anticipated to lower the rising number of graduates who meet the minimum requirements set by the sector. This serves as a conduit between employers and employees (Azman, et al., 2020).

To improve the quality of education institution, it is believed that there should be a full attention to the 9 (nine) key factors to a quality link and match between education institution and the industrial world (Ali et al., 2019); these such as: (1) the improvement of knowledge and skill through the development of human resources in sound policy and methods, (2) the construction of curriculum which is routinely evaluated and revised to reflect changes in learning and teaching strategies, the demands of the labor market and industry, globalization, and the industrial revolution, (3) developing a range of adaptable teaching and learning techniques that take into account the various requirements and learning preferences of students, (4) relevant collaboration between educational institutions and business that includes business professionals in curriculum policy formulation and the teaching and learning process, (5) a good accreditation system to raise the standards and make them pertinent to business demands and the labor market, (6) to maximize cooperation with business and related parties in managing and sharing resources contained in joint financing, use professional funding and quality management, (7) to ensure the sustainability of all learning and service processes, teachers and staff development, (8) outstanding academic environment and culture to equip students and graduates with the soft skills necessary for the industry, and (9) infrastructure and facilities to support the laboratory's theory-and-practice learning process.

Students' Competency

Competence is defined as a person's capacity to apply their knowledge, as well as their performance of skills and talents, as their traits that are associated to superior performance in a task they execute, and can be present in a variety of contexts (Gonczi, 2004; Mulyasa, 2004; Delamare and Winterton, 2005). Bargon (2002) adds that competences necessary for someone to carry out a task or job that are based on the knowledge, abilities, and attitude suitable for carrying out the required work; demonstrated the capacity to gather, organize, and transmit information. They were also able to plan and coordinate activities in coordination with other individuals and organizations. They were also able to use technology to address problems. Develop and create standards of competence means the ability to provide standards that are applicable to business, corporate, and industrial settings. John Dewey in Mulder (2017) mentions about competency instead of competence and about the need for education to enable the development of 'industrial competency' so that people should develop competence to choose and pursue a career. These Deweyan ideas are closely related to the present core skills in the areas of career, citizenship, and self-control. In general, competence is characterized as the general ability of individuals to carry out tasks satisfactorily and as an aspect of competence. A skilled professional is competent in that sense and possesses a range of competencies.

The integrated occupationalist approach to competence development situates competency-based vocational and professional education. Three approaches of competence can be distinguished as follows: (1) competence and behavioristic functionalism; (2) competence as integrated occupationalism; and, (3) competence as situated professionalism. Competence-oriented education is instruction for which a competency framework—the dot on the horizon—is constructed. The framework is used to define intended learning outcomes and coordinate assessment strategies and methods, but the way learning activities are organized is mostly left unaffected. The European Qualifications Framework (EQF) covers a competency framework that is frequently applied in educational programs that emphasize competence, including those for vocational and professional education. The 'competences' in the EQF are specified as follows: (1) working or studying in a structured setting while being directly supervised; (2) supervised work or study with some autonomy; (3) assume accountability for finishing assignments at work or in your studies; (4) practice self-control under the constraints of environments for work or study that are often predictable but subject to change; (5) practice management and supervision in situations when there is unpredictable change throughout work or study activities; (6) manage intricate technical or professional tasks or projects, taking charge of decision-making in erratic work- or study-related situations; (7) manage and transform complicated, unpredictable, and circumstances that call for innovative strategic methods at work or in your studies; (8) exhibit significant authority, independence and creativity, scholarly and professional integrity, and an ongoing dedication to the advancement of novel concepts or methods in contexts of work or study, including research (Mulder, 2017).

Teaching and Learning Method

Among the various methods used in education institutions, there are 3 (three) major methods encouraged to be used at Politeknik Negeri Bali, these include: student-centered learning, project-based learning (PjBL), and experiential learning which are discussed in the following.

Student-centered Learning

The entire process of teaching and learning should be planned for the students' ability to comprehend the competencies imparted as a whole and to develop the abilities necessary to foster the achievement of the standards required in the workplace. Implementing student-centered learning (SCL) is one of the current trends in education. SCL's goal is to make the classroom and its students come to life (Overby, 2011). The way that the teaching experience is organized and set up, with an emphasis on the roles that students play in the learning process, taking into account the interests, wants, and demands of the learners. This method factors the various learning styles and methods suitable for students while planning instructional experiences. This method yields more results and proven to be more fruitful as students are not simply memorizing learning (Zühal, 2012). The advent of the competency-based approach has had a considerable impact on student-centered learning (SCL) in recent years (Abdigapbarova & Zhiyenbayeva, 2022). As an alternative to the more conventional teacher-centered method of instruction, the paradigm shift to SCL has been promoted, with its focus on the learner who is active and responsible for his or her learning and where information is built rather than conveyed (Brush & Saye, 2000).

In SCL, the teacher no longer acts as the owner of knowledge but as a facilitator of learning who views students as learners who need to be guided through their intellectual development process rather than as individuals lacking any kind of knowledge (Wright, 2011). The development of learning opportunities that cultivate the competencies that the students require to succeed in the workplace is essential in facilitating this transformation (Francis, Ngugi & Kinzi, 2017). While the teacher encourages them to take ownership of their education, students become the core of the learning process. With this idea, educators should create educational activities that encourage students to take more ownership of their learning and engage in social interaction

(Jacobsen, 2009). Maintaining common-sense in the classroom is crucial in SCL because teachers should be able to change dull, lifeless settings into vibrant, authentic spaces that are rich in relationships (Uhl, 2010; Overby, 2011). This has been shown to help students reach better levels of critical thinking, problem-solving, learning attitude, and overall attendance. By enabling students to effectively work on complicated, open-ended problems that are authentically associated with certain practices, culture, or processes, these environments support students' self-directed learning (Land et al., 2012).

Priyatmojo (2010) posits that SCL has four advantages as follows: (1) improving students' ability to think through the sharing of ideas between students; (2) fostering in students' sense of acceptance, sympathy, sensitivity, and respect for other people's viewpoints; (3) gaining knowledge as a result of the ability to exchange and receive information; and, (4) providing students with new knowledge. He continues saying that in order to have a successful SCL class; it is important to pay attention to a number of terms and circumstances. These conditions include: (1) heterogenous grouping of students in terms of their knowledge, analytical skills, and ethnic differences, (2) detailed explanation of tasks and learning structures, (3) prior learning experience of the students, (4) provided access to contribute or speak fairly, (5) contribution of each students on their opinions, (6) capability to explain reasoning on their opinions, (7) willingness of each student to listen and comment on their friends' opinions, (8) acceptance of list of opinions or ideas by all group members as the results of the discussions, and (9) mutual understanding support atmosphere on the learning process.

According to Guidance on Educational Technology in Higher Vocational Education (Buku Panduan Teknologi Pembelajaran Pendidikan Tinggi Vokasi) by Direktorat Jendral Pembelajaran dan Kemahasiswaan (2016), there are various SCL methods that can be applied in any classrooms, such as small group discussion, role play and simulation, case study, discovery learning (DL), self-directed learning (SDL), cooperative learning (CL), collaborative learning (CbL), contextual instruction (CI), project-based learning (PjBL), and problem-based learning and inquiry (PBL).

Project-based Learning (PjBL)

Project-based learning (PjBL) is a kind of instruction that actively involves students, in which the study is centered on them, these are marked by autonomy, productive explorations, goal-setting, cooperation, communication, and reflection within practical applications (Kotsaki et al., 2016). According to Guidance on Educational Technology in Higher Vocational Education (Buku Panduan Teknologi Pembelajaran Pendidikan Tinggi Vokasi) by Direktorat Jendral Pembelajaran dan Kemahasiswaan (2016); this approach enables students to complete projects that have been carefully planned out before being asked to make a responsible presentation in a forum. In addition to planning a methodical and carefully calculated project, the students will also follow a series of steps in a difficult yet organized inquiry investigation before formulation, under lecturers' advisory and assessments. Project-based learning (PjBL) is often thought of as a teaching strategy in which students respond to real-world concerns or challenges through an extended inquiry process (Lattimer and Riordan, 2011). PjBL structures instruction around projects and places students in real-world settings where they can investigate challenging issues that are related to the professional practice they are preparing for (Hârtescu, 2014). PjBL fosters students' critical thinking abilities while also fostering their creativity, encouraging teamwork, and empowering them to independently locate and present the knowledge they have learned. PjBL typically requires students to voluntarily participate in the suggested meaningful learning activities, which are primarily collaboration (Bédard, 2012).

Students learn largely through knowledge construction and meaning formation in PjBL environments through iterative processes of questioning, active learning, sharing, and reflection. The focus of service learning is on interdisciplinary, collaborative, student-centered, and integrated with real-world concerns and practices educational possibilities. According to reports, this method is popular and widely employed in a range of school settings. Jalinus et al. (2017) on their research revealed the seven steps to an effective Project-Based Learning model; which include: (1) formulating the expected learning outcome, (2) understanding the concept of the teaching materials, (3) skills training, (4) designing the project theme, (5) making the project proposal, (6) executing the tasks of projects, and (7) presentation of the project report. Their research shown that the seven PjBL procedures might be effectively used to improve students' productive competence. Meanwhile based on Guidance on Educational Technology in Higher Vocational Education (2016), it is stated that this method should be implemented and done in at least 2 (two) semesters and it is assumed that the students are theoretically ready and having the expertise. In accordance with Bloom's taxonomy, PjBL method is classified as the realization of application, analysis, evaluation and creating. Project can be given as a collection of several subjects related in order to solve specific problem(s). Flowchart may be needed to point out the problems before it is set out in a planning in form of diagram blocks. Each block is then broken down into related stages or functions that is assessable to shed light its appropriateness to the expected result.

Experiential Learning

The experiential learning approach emphasizes the creation of information via first-hand experience and can be used in vocational education. This demonstrates that practical activities make up a large amount of the vocational learning characteristics when compared to theoretical ones. The emphasis of the experiential learning approach is on the value of active experience and student participation. Students will develop self-efficacy through authentic practice-based learning, which in turn results in their confidence to tackle a particular task. This teaching strategy is anticipated to enhance student learning outcomes and foster the growth of their cognitive and psychomotor abilities (Pamungkas et al., 2019).

Experiential learning is a holistic educational structure that is demanded by many education stakeholders, according to Kolb's Experiential Learning Theory (ELT), is defined as a "Process wherein knowledge is formed through the transformation of experience". Experiential instruction is characterized by: (1) a continuous learning process grounded in experience; (2) a process requiring the resolution of conflicts between dialectically opposed modes of adapting to the world; (3) a holistic process of adapting to the world; (d) learning involves transactions between the person and the environment, and (4) a process of creating knowledge (Kolb in Baker and Robinson, 2016). When learning is seen from the experiential perspective, the emphasis is more on the process than the results, emphasizing the growth of metacognitive abilities essential to lifelong learning (Baker et al. 2012).

Analysis by Morris (2019) on experience learning of Kolb's model as an experiential learning cycle, revealed five themes: (1) learners are involved and active participants; (2) knowledge is situation in place and time; (3) learners are exposed to novel experiences, which involves risk; (4) learning demands inquiry to specific real-world problems; and (5) critical reflection acts as a mediator of meaningful learning. As a result, a modification to Kolb's model is suggested: experiential learning entails concrete experience that is rich in context, critical reflecting observation, abstract conceptualization that is specific to context, and practical active experimentation.

Figure 2. Kolb's cycle of experiential learning (Pamungkas et al., 2019, p.030023-2)

Rethinking curriculum design to accommodate experiential learning methods is necessary. This study demonstrates that the direct instruction technique to teaching, which is used by the great majority of curriculum resources now available to instructors, however, it is insufficient when used alone. In order to ensure that all four learning modes are covered, the instructional assistance and materials for the variety of experiences must be made available. As Dewey (1938) indicated, knowledge cannot be attained solely by experience. To qualify as experiential learning, an event must be well-planned by the teacher of a high standard and result in learning.

Method

This study uses a qualitative approach; the research is conducted at Tourism Department Politeknik Negeri Bali. Data on the business activities that have been initiated and carried out at the school are collected using in-depth-interview, observation and direct participation. The interviewees include students and lecturers of Tourism Department Politeknik Negeri Bali. Observation and direct participation are based on the fact that the authors are the staff members of the school. The data collected include: the business activities practices before and after the Politeknik Negeri Bali becoming Public Service Institution (BLU) and the launching of MBKM by the Ministry of Education and Culture, Research and Technology of Indonesia. The approach used in this study is the assessment of data about the business practices carried out and initiated at the PNB Campus and the assessment include the leverage and the challenge faced when operating business at campus.

Results and Discussion

Initially, before the implementation of MBKM and BLU (Public Service Institution) at Bali State Polytechnic, the outflow of students' products created during the Lab practices are distributed in an ad hoc – non-routine mode; when there are student practices for the subject of Event and MICE (Meeting Incentives Conventions and Exhibition), even though there is a need to show and share the practices results to public or market regularly. This distribution is mainly carried out in synergy with the subject of MICE Practices, which are scheduled in accordance with MICE/Event Subject Lesson Plan. The financial margin when available is reinvested to the activities, and there is no sustainable administration and bookkeeping related to these ad hoc business activities.

After the BLU and the MBKM, the business activities are encouraged and intended to be more routine, regular, and well-administrated, in which students and lectures can actively participate in a real-life business practice regardless of the scope. A smaller scope could be initiated and later can be developed into a more complex structure. Moreover, being a BLU Institution makes room for this private business venture, and the MBKM National Policy gives flexibility and makes the advancement of the business practices management and operations carried out in Politeknik Negeri Bali is possible to be implemented.

Currently, F&B Teaching Factory (TeFA) outlet has been established with the assistance of Directorate General of Vocational Education under the stage of trial opening. The TeFa is still in minimum-level of operating mood aiming at transactions, yet it is still far from being well-managed. Thus, identified challenge faced by the institutions. Tourism Department is to operate a real business unit integrating all the aspects of teaching and learning process of the relevant subjects, and in support to achieving the vision and mission of the institution as well as being the BLU (public service institution).

Ideally, how TeFa should work with the overall objectives: (1) to graduate better professionals by providing leading edge concepts in modern manufacturing, enabling them to effectively compete in today's industry; (2) to enhance the current curriculum that will focus on modern manufacturing concepts; (3) to demonstrate viable solutions to the dynamics of technological challenges across the entire integrated business enterprise; (4) to transfer technology and information from and to partner companies as well as local companies, with student activities, team projects and senior projects as the primary vehicle (Alptekin et al., 2001). On contrary, Mavrikios et al. (2018) have identified the diverse challenges, starting from gaps and shortages of workforce skills and competences to novel knowledge delivery mechanisms and utilizing modern ICTs that have to be used. Therefore, the results of the qualitative data analysis is presented in the Table 1 below.

Leverage

According to Alptekin et al. (2001), the overall objectives of the Teaching Factory are: (1) to produce better professionals by teaching cutting-edge manufacturing techniques that will allow them to successfully compete in the market today; (2) to improve the current program, which will emphasize concepts from modern manufacturing; (3) to show practical ways of addressing the constant technology issues that face the entire integrated business enterprise; and, (4) to transmit technology and knowledge from and to local businesses as well as partners, with the main vehicles being student activities, team projects, and senior projects.

Those objectives support the leverages of Food and Beverage Teaching Factory (TeFa) that directs business aspect as the medium for students to learn about the study program competencies in a real business environment. Besides, it is an outflow medium for students produce during students' practice to reach the market, community or the institution/business partners in the tourism industry. As Politeknik Negeri Bali is now a BLU, this TeFa project could improve and potential for profit. The actions and plan that are supporting not only the curricula, but also the process to shape students to be ready-to-work graduates as well. The blueprint itself is integrated with the policy applied in Politeknik Negeri Bali that is integrated with national implementation toward achieving the vision of the institution and the ministry. Moreover, it is also to building entrepreneur mentality for the graduates of Politeknik Negeri Bali.

Table 1. Leverages and Challenges of F&B TeFa in Politeknik Negeri Bali

A Leverage	A Challenge
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Business aspect is the medium for students to learn about the study program competencies in a real business environment.	The conventional mindset of the Civitas academic: students and lectures, and administration staff on operating a real-business entity in this context the TeFa Food outlet.
It is an outflow medium for students produce during students' laboratory practice to reach the market, community or the institution/business partners in the tourism industry.	Operational mechanism setup as well as products and vendors that should match the market quality, especially partner companies, and not limited to the physical aspects of TeFa and its facilities setup.
Potential for profit support Politeknik Negeri Bali as a BLU.	Administration and its Software development needs to be installed.
The actions and plan that are supportive not only for the curricula, but also the teaching and learning process to shape students to become a ready-to-work graduate.	Integration of the business unit operation with the MBKM curriculum and the semester lesson plan of the related subjects specifically at the practical aspects.
The blueprint is integrated with the policy applied in Politeknik Negeri Bali.	Management setup integrating with PNB as a BLU institution needs to be developed.
Integrated with National Policy Implementation toward achieving the Vision of the Directorate General of Vocational Education	Integration of the implementation of the Semester Lesson Plan of the relevant subjects with the yearly program of the Study Programs within Tourism Department PNB.
Building entrepreneur mentality for the graduates of Politeknik Negeri Bali.	Manufacture production mood of Human Resource

Challenges

The mindset of the existing human resources and establishing the operating mechanism of the business unit at the education institutions are the main challenge identified by Mavrikios et al. (2018). The Food Tefa operation at Tourism Department PNB also identifies a similar notion even revealing a more complex situation. The adapting the mindset of the academic members lectures, students and administration staff on operating a real-business entity becomes the main challenge. Operational and managerial mechanism setup being integrated with the PNB as an overall institution, study program and departmental level needs to be developed and established. Products and vendors that match the market nature, especially partner companies, and not limited to the physical aspects of TeFa and its facilities standard. Administration and its trickledown subsequences aiming at a smooth-running day to day operation including hardware and software development and installation to meet the learning standard needs to be established. Integration of the business unit operation with the MBKM curriculum and the semester lesson plan of the related subjects specifically at the practical aspects is also a vital aspect to be addressed. The implementation of the Semester Lesson Plan of the relevant subjects with the yearly program of the Study Programs within Tourism Department PNB needs to be integrated. And not the least the management setup integrating with PNB as a BLU institution needs to be developed which give the Food Tefa its legal stand.

Conclusion

Despite of all the challenges faced mainly in the area of supporting human resources, operation and management mechanism of the business unit, integrating business practices within an education institution brings significant benefit to the quality of education institution in overall scheme and in developing ready and competent human resource supporting the industry. As this practice is just initiated, thus, this practice should be perfected in order to bring maximum benefits.

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